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RESEARCH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HEMOSTATIC CAPSULES

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ABSTRACT

The concept of development of the national pharmaceutical industry is based on solving the following tasks: -creation of original medicines based on biologically active substances isolated from medicinal plants growing in Uzbekistan; Nevertheless, studies aimed at creating domestic effective drugs based on medicinal raw materials and technologies for their production are relevant. In this regard, the development of herbal dosage forms in various finished dosage forms for prevention and treatment is one of the most urgent scientific and practical tasks. The aim of the study was to create easy-to-use, characterized by sufficient bioavailability and storage stability of hemostatic drug capsules.

Keywords: hemostatic agents, blood vessels, bleeding, pharmacology, clinical indications, thrombogenic agents, acetylsalicylic acid.

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ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В ОБЛАСТИ РАЗРАБОТКИ ГЕМОСТАТИЧЕСКИХ КАПСУЛ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Концепция развития национальной фармацевтической отрасли основывается на решении следующих задач: -создание оригинальных лекарственных средств на основе биологически активных веществ, выделенных из лекарственных растений, произрастающих в Узбекистане; тем не менее, исследования, направленные на создание отечественных эффективных лекарственных препаратов на основе лекарственного сырья и технологий их производства, являются актуальными. В связи с этим разработка растительных лекарственных форм в различных готовых лекарственных формах для профилактики и лечения является одной из наиболее актуальных научно-практических задач. Целью исследования явилось, создание удобных в применении, отличающейся достаточной биологической доступностью стабильностью при хранении капсул гемостатического препарата.

Ключевые слова: гемостатические средства, сосуды, кровотечения, фармакология, клинические показания, тромбообразующие средства, ацетилсалициловая кислота.

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GEMOSTATIK KAPSULALARNI ISHLAB CHIQISHDAGI TADQIQOTLAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Milliy farmatsevtika sanoatini rivojlantirish konsepsiyasi quyidagi vazifalarni hal etishga asoslangan: -O‘zbekistonda o‘sadigan dorivor o‘simliklardan ajratib olingan biologik faol moddalar asosida original dori vositalarini yaratish; Shunga qaramay, dorivor xom ashyo va ularni ishlab chiqarish texnologiyalari asosida mahalliy samarali dori vositalarini yaratishga qaratilgan tadqiqotlar dolzarb hisoblanadi. Shu munosabat bilan profilaktika va davolash uchun har xil tayyor dori shakllarida o‘simlik dori shakllarini ishlab chiqish eng dolzarb ilmiy va amaliy vazifalardan biridir. Tadqiqot maqsadi gemostatik dori kapsulalarining etarli bio-mavjudligi va saqlash barqarorligi bilan tavsiflangan foydalanish uchun qulay bo‘lgan mahsulotni yaratish edi.

Kalit so‘zlar: gemostatik vositalar, qon tomirlari, qon ketishi, farmakologiya, klinik ko‘rsatkichlar, trombojenik vositalar, asetilsalitsil kislotasi.

Introduction. Health is one of the most essential blessings for human life. In this sense, the attention and care paid by the President to the healthcare system in the new period of development serves to protect the health of the population, further increase the welfare of our people, the gradual elimination of problems in the system. It should be noted that each medical worker has a special place and contribution to the achievements in the field. Pharmaceuticals are an integral part of medicine. If we continue our opinion with the evidence related to pharmaceuticals. From our observations, it is clear that most of our compatriots go to the doctor, at least once, in the hope of finding a cure for the disease. Because there are many people among our people who prefer to be cured on the basis of various natural herbs and tinctures, rather than chemically prepared drugs. Speaking about the urgency of the issue, the most reliable and effective way to protect the health of the population in the current situation is to expand the production of high quality products based on natural, pure medicinal plants grown in our country. Provision of cheap and high-quality medicines is a priority in our country.

The signing of the Presidential Decree "On additional measures for the accelerated development of the pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2022-2026" was another important step in the development of the industry. The measures outlined in this document provide for the provision of benefits to enterprises in the industry, thereby tripled production, increasing the level of supply of the domestic market with quality and affordable pharmaceutical products to 80%. The volume of pharmaceutical production has almost doubled. It is no coincidence that the task has been set to triple this figure in the next 5 years. Another analysis of medicine: there is a growing need for hemostatic drugs in medical practice today. In all surgical procedures performed during childbirth, hemostatic agents should be in reserve. It is no exaggeration to say that this is one of the main and primary factors in saving human life[2,3].

The purpose of the study: In this regard, the development of herbal dosage forms in various finished dosage forms for prevention and treatment is one of the most urgent scientific and practical tasks. The object of the study was the substance Glilagin, created on the basis of glycyram and lagochilin from medicinal plant materials and developed by employees of the A. Sadykov Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Synthesized supramolecular complexes based on glycyrrhizic acid (GA), its monoammonium salt with lagochiline dissolve in water, which increases the bioavailability of these complexes, and pharmacological studies have also proven their hemostatic activity. The subject of the study is research on the development of the composition and rational technology of the encapsulated dosage form, quality control, biopharmaceutical research and the study of stability.

Materials and research methods. Glilagin capsule is a new drug in the group of hemostatic drugs. Therefore, the research topic is devoted to these topical issues. The main active ingredient of the glylagin capsule is Lagoxilin and the excipient is glycyrrhizic acid, which are recommended for bleeding from the uterus, lungs, nose and other organs.

Many new groups of hemostatic drugs are currently being recommended. During the creation of drug forms from such substances, the most moderate of a number of bases are selected in order to maintain its therapeutic properties and increase bioavailability. Drugs belonging to this group are referred to in medical practice as hemostatic drugs. These include vitamin K preservatives, herbal preparations that reduce vascular wall permeability, and fibrinolysis agents [4,5].

Vitamin K preservatives (vikasol, glilagin) are prescribed for bleeding and its prevention (before surgery). Vitamin K is abundant in nature and is mainly found in the green part of plants. It is involved in the process of stopping blood flow, blood clotting. Therefore, herbal medicines containing this vitamin are mainly used as a means of stopping blood flow. Of course, as everyone has their own goals, the development of Glilagin capsule composition technology and quality assessment based on relevant regulatory documents is the main goal of my research work.

I aimed to accomplish a number of tasks to achieve the goal. In particular, the study of physicochemical properties of the substance Glilagin, obtaining capsules with different bases, selection of the optimal composition based on the quality and quantity of the obtained capsule, as well as in vitro assessment of the bioavailability and shelf life of the selected optimal content capsule.

The developed drug is even more important as it expands the range of hemostatic drugs for the production of pharmaceutical companies in Uzbekistan.

When developing encapsulated dosage forms, it is of great importance to know the composition of the encapsulated mass and its characteristics. To substantiate the composition and technology of capsules, the physicochemical and technological properties of the substance were studied. The main characteristics of the substance were studied according to the methods given in the State Pharmacopoeia.

The flowability of the studied masses was studied on a VP-12A device according to the method developed at the All-Russian Research Institute of Chemistry and Technology of Medicines. The study on bulk density was carried out on the device. Compressibility and ejection force were determined by the well-known method given in the regulatory documentation, the moisture content on the moisture meter.

As can be seen from the above data, the mass has insufficient flowability, poor compressibility and a fairly high moisture content.

A capsule dosage form, unlike others, does not require the mandatory introduction of excipients if the medicinal products have satisfactory technological characteristics. They can be directly filled into gelatin capsules, which greatly simplifies the production process. In addition, take into account the fact that capsule machines operate on the principle of complete filling of the capsule volume. If this condition is not met, it is necessary to introduce excipients that would improve the technological properties of drugs. To do this, fillers should be introduced to fill the entire volume of the capsule. To determine the type and number of excipients in the development of capsules with glycyram, the physicochemical and technological properties of the active substance were taken into account. Various excipients recommended by SP XI were used, both individually and in combinations: glucose, lactose, sucrose, potato starch, corn starch, microcrystalline cellulose, carboxymethyl cellulose, calcium carbonate, magnesium stearate, calcium stearate, stearic acid, aerosil.

In the development of drugs, excipients play an important role, the choice of which for each dosage form should be justified by assessing the physicochemical and technological characteristics, studying their effect on the efficacy, safety and stability of drugs. Determination of technological indicators of the quality of model mixtures was carried out according to generally accepted methods [1].

To select the technology for manufacturing Glilagin capsules, the following technological characteristics of the substance were determined: residual moisture, flowability without vibration and with vibration, bulk density before and after compaction, which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Technological properties of the substance Glilagin

Characteristics, units of measurement	Results
Appearance	White powder with a light yellow tint
Residual humidity, %	0,09±0,004
Bulk density, g/cm ³ : without seal with seal	0,267±0,008 0,425±0,018
Flowability, g/s: no vibration with vibration	Is absent Is absent

It has been established that the Glilagin substance has poor flowability and low bulk density. In this regard, to improve the technological properties, it is necessary to add loosening and antifriction auxiliary substances.

The analysis of these data showed the need to use excipients that would reduce the clumping of the substance, reduce the moisture absorption activity and improve its flowability in the production of capsules.

Conclusion. The technological properties of the encapsulated mass have been studied. Taking into account the obtained data predetermines the addition of appropriate excipients. These technological operations can also significantly affect the therapeutic efficacy and bioavailability of pharmacologically active substances.

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